

FAST PREDICTION OF THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS FROM HEAT BUILD-UP MEASUREMENTS: FROM THE SAMPLE TO THE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue design of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics (SFRT) components for structural applications in the automotive industry requires an accurate knowledge of the numerous factors affecting the fatigue lifetime (manufacturing process, loading type, environment, etc). First, this paper aims at describing a method based on thermal measurements (using an infrared camera) that reduces substantially the characterization duration of the fatigue properties compare to classical methods. In this study, a simple way to get the cyclic dissipated energy from thermal measurements is suggested, usable for homogeneous and heterogeneous dissipation fields. A so-called “heat build-up protocol” is used to relate the cyclic stress amplitude to the cyclic dissipated energy. The second purpose of this paper is to characterize the fatigue behavior of two families of samples. The first geometry is a classical Dogbone-shaped samples. The mean fiber orientation is aligned with the injection flow and with the solicitation direction. The second geometry is more complex and intends to be representative of some specific geometric details found on industrial parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastics (SFRT) provide today a major opportunity to obtain lightweight automotive parts for a reasonable cost. Since a few years this kind of materials is used for structural components in automotive applications. Under service conditions these parts are submitted to cyclic loadings and environmental conditions (temperature and humidity ratio) and the fatigue design of SFRT components for structural applications in the automotive industry requires an accurate knowledge of the numerous factors affecting the fatigue lifetime (manufacturing process, loading type, environment, etc) [1]. First, this paper aims at describing a method based on thermal measurements (using an infrared camera) that reduces substantially the characterization duration of the fatigue properties compare to classical methods. Recent publications illustrated the relevancy of using an energy based criterion to predict the fatigue properties [2]. In this study, a simple way to get the cyclic dissipated energy from thermal measurements is suggested, usable for homogeneous and heterogeneous dissipation fields. A so-called “heat build-up protocol” is used to relate the cyclic stress amplitude to the cyclic dissipated energy. The second purpose of this paper is to characterize the fatigue behavior of two families of samples. The first geometry is a classical Dogbone-shaped samples obtained by milling of injected plates. The mean fiber orientation is aligned with the injection flow and with the tensile direction. The second geometry is more complex and intends to be representative of some specific geometric details found on industrial parts. In the case presented here, we focus on thickness reduction or expansion. The sample is injected from one of its ends. Both kinds of samples were conditioned under a humidity ratio of 50% (the material is PA66GF50).The samples are submitted to cyclic tensile loadings with a load ratio of $R=0$. A first conclusion is drawn on the ability of the approach to predict accurately the fatigue properties on standard and structural samples. The access to the dissipation fields is obviously a key point for this prediction. A second conclusion can be obtained from the possibility to apply a fatigue criterion obtained from Dogbone sample on structural ones, opening the way to structures validation.

2 SAMPLES CONSIDERED

Two kinds of samples are considered (the material is PA66GF50), the first one is a classical Dogbone-shaped samples obtained by milling of injected plates (called in the following **Dogbone** samples). The mean fiber orientation is aligned with the injection flow and with the tensile direction. The second geometry is more complex and intends to be representative of some specific geometric details found on industrial parts. In the case presented here, we focus on thickness reduction or expansion (called in the following **Wavy 1** samples). The sample is injected from one of its ends (see **fig. 1**).

Figure 1. Geometrical and loading features of the Dogbone and Wavy 1 samples.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

3.1 Experimental set-up

The tests are performed with an INSTRON materials servo-hydraulic machine (capacity of 100KN), a FLIR Systems SC7600BB infrared camera and a contact extensometer are used to record thermo-mechanical data (see **fig. 2**). All the fatigue tests are achieved at room temperature (around 23°C).

Figure 2. Experimental set-up and observed zones (with the infrared camera).

3.2 Thermal measurements

The thermal acquisition is performed using a FLIR SC7600BB infrared camera. This device is equipped with a FPA (focal plane array) of 640×512 pixels, sensitive in the 1.5-5μm spectral band with a spatial resolution of 15μm. The focal length of the optical lens used is 50 mm and its transmittivity is 0.94. For all the experiments, the integration time is set to 1800 μs.

In order to improve the thermal resolution (compared to classical calibration), a homemade pixelwise calibration (with an extra correction taking into account the influence of the internal camera temperature) is used here. The calibration is performed thanks to a HGH DCN1000 N4 extended black body whose emissivity is 0.98±0.02 and thermal stability is ±0.02°C. Each pixel of the FPA has his own polynome linking the temperature to the digital level [3]:

$$T(i, j) = \sum_{n=0}^4 \left[\sum_{m=0}^2 a_{n,m}(i, j) [T_{cam} - T_{cam}^0]^m \right] DL(i, j)^n \quad (1)$$

where T_{cam}^0 is a reference internal temperature of the camera set to 30 °C, T_{cam} is the actual internal temperature of the device, DL are the raw measurement data and $a_{n,m}$ are the coefficient of the polynome. Therefore, each polynome has 15 coefficients. They are identified thanks to a series of images corresponding to regularly-spaced temperatures of the black body over the range 15°C–40°C and for various internal camera temperatures ranging from 24°C (obtained once the camera has just been switched on) to 36°C (obtained several hours after being switched on), the protocol of the identification of the coefficients can be found in [3]. After this specific calibration, a resolution of about 10 mK is obtained in differential measurements.

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL AND ANALYSIS OF THE HEAT BUILD-UP

4.1 Experimental protocol

The samples are submitted to several blocks of cyclic tensile loadings and the mechanical and thermal data are recorded with a frequency of 20Hz. The cyclic tensile tests are achieved with a loading frequency of 1Hz and a loading ratio of R=0, each loading step (composed of 20 loading cycles and 5 minutes of cooling) is performed for several stress amplitudes (see **fig. 3**). The extensometer gives access to the average strain over a length of 12.5mm and the mean nominal stress is evaluated from the force measured divided by the initial cross-section of the gage length area. It is important to notice that in this protocol the last loading step runs until the failure of the sample.

4.2 Determination of the dissipated energy per cycle

The thermodynamics of irreversible processes is used here to analyze the thermal results. The thermodynamical equilibrium state of a volume element is defined at each instant t by the current value of a set of variables, namely T the temperature, ε a strain tensor and V_k the internal variables. Internal variables are chosen in accordance with the physical mechanisms within the studied material. The first and second principles of thermodynamics are then checked in order to define the evolution of the variables [5].

Considering the heat equation (see **fig. 4 and Table 1**), some hypothesis can be applied: the external heat supply is not time dependant, the temperature rise (under 0.5°C here) is low enough to neglect the couplings between the temperature variation and the internal variables and to neglect the variation of ρ and C . Defining λ the conductivity tensor, considered isotropic $\lambda = \lambda \mathbf{1}$ and using the Fourier's law, the heat equation writes [3-4].

$$\rho C \dot{T} - \lambda \Delta T = \Delta + r + \rho T \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial \varepsilon \partial T} : \dot{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

In this study, only cyclic tests are considered. As the external heat supply is considered constant and as the thermoelastic coupling terms compensate over a mechanical cycle, solving the heat equation over a mechanical cycle reduces to solve:

$$\rho C \dot{\tilde{\theta}} - \lambda \Delta \tilde{\theta} = \tilde{\Delta} \quad (4)$$

Where $\tilde{\theta}$ and $\tilde{\Delta}$ represent the mean temperature variation and the mean dissipated energy over time for one mechanical cycle (T is the period), i.e.:

$$\tilde{\theta} = \frac{1}{T} \int_{cycle} \theta(t) dt \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{\Delta} = \frac{1}{T} \int_{cycle} \Delta(t) dt \quad (6)$$

To solve the Eq. 4, many different approaches are possible; in this paper the one presented in [4] has been chosen. In this approach, the temperature variation rate is calculated for $t \rightarrow t_0$ where t_0 is the initial time (of loading). Assuming that the chosen instants are close enough so that the thermal exchanges do not have the time to occur and considering well chosen instants at the same mechanical configurations (peaks on the figure 5), the heat equation writes:

$$\rho C \dot{\theta}_0 = \tilde{\Delta} \quad (7)$$

Where $\dot{\theta}_0$ is the initial temperature variation rate calculated over instants at the same mechanical configuration (called in the following ‘‘theta dot’’).

This equation is written for time dependant variables, considering cyclic solicitations and assuming that $\tilde{\Delta}$ is constant for each cycle, it is of course convenient to use the dissipated energy per cycle Δ^* and the frequency f_r to write:

$$\rho C \dot{\theta}_0 = f_r \Delta^* \quad (8)$$

Figure 3. Heat build-up test.

Figure 4. Heat equation.

Figure 5. Instants at the same mechanical configuration during the loading cycles (peaks).

Symbol	Quantity	SI Units
T	Temperature	K
C	Specific heat capacity	$JKg^{-1}K^{-1}$
ρ	Density	Kgm^{-3}
θ	Temperature variation	K
Ψ	Thermodynamic free energy	JKg^{-1}
\vec{q}	Heat flux density	Wm^{-2}
ε	Strain tensor	
V_k	Internal variables	Various
Δ	Dissipated energy	Wm^{-3}
Δ^*	Dissipated energy per cycle	Jm^{-3}
$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \dot{\theta}$	Theta dot	Ks^{-1}

Table 1. Nomenclature.

5. MECHANICAL AND THERMAL DATA OBTAINED FROM THE TESTS

Several kinds of curves can be plotted using the mechanical data. For example, the nominal stress-nominal strain curve (see **fig. 6**) and the evolution of the hysteresis area (calculated using numerical methods) along the test (see **fig. 7**). In those curves a shift of the hysteretic loop (residual strain) is noticed and two regimes in the hysteresis area evolution, the first regime (transient state, until the fourth cycle) shows an evolving hysteresis area, the second regime (steady state, from the fourth cycle to the twentieth cycle) shows a constant hysteresis area (for both families of samples). The secant modulus (E_s) along the tests can be also plotted. The way to evaluate the secant modulus is shown on the figure 8. To compare the dissipated energy per cycle calculated with the mechanical (hysteresis area) and the thermal data, the cycles having a stable hysteresis area must be considered (steady state). Therefore the cycles 4 to 10 are used for these calculations. The value of the “theta dot” can be calculated from the slope of the temperature evolution (blue line in the figure 9), and, thereafter, the dissipated energy per cycle (see **eq. 8**).

Figure 6. Illustration of the stress-strain curves along a loading step.

Figure 7. Illustration of the hysteresis area evolution for several loading steps.

Figure 8. Secant modulus evaluation.

Figure 9. Illustration of the theta dot evaluation.

6. FIELD OF CYCLIC DISSIPATED ENERGY

6.1 Illustration

Using the method described in the sections 4 and 5, it is possible to obtain the dissipated energy per cycle averaged over a defined zone but it is not possible to have information about the field of cyclic dissipated energy. To have a good approximation of the field of cyclic dissipated energy, a method is illustrated on the figure 10. In this example, the averaged temperature evolution is obtained over a portion of the sample (black rectangle), then the images corresponding to the forth and the tenth cycle can be determined (images 1 and 2 on the figure 10) from the peaks observed. The subtraction of the temperature fields for these 2 images gives the temperature variation field (image 3 on the figure 10), finally the image of the temperature variation can be used to get the field of cyclic dissipated energy (image 4 on the figure 10), by dividing the field by the time between the forth and the tenth cycle (6 seconds for a frequency of 1 Hz) and by multiplying by the density and the specific heat capacity (see Eq. 8).

Figure 10. Field of cyclic dissipated energy.

6.2 Analysis of the thermal conduction and the thermal exchange

The choice of the peaks (images 1 and 2 on the figure 10), obviously affects the estimation of the cyclic dissipated energy. As the basic idea is to work here in a nearly adiabatic state it is mandatory to compare the characteristic thermal times to the mechanical time (1s minimum between two comparable mechanical states, as the frequency is set to 1 Hz) [4]. First, the characteristic time for the thermal exchange was evaluated from the evolution of the temperature along time during the cooling steps of the heat build-up test. A classical exponential identification [2] fitted the curves well and a value of around 200s was found for the case of dogbone samples and of around 300s for the Wavy 1 samples. The adiabatic hypothesis seems therefore checked moreover the characteristic time for conduction can be evaluated using the physical parameters (density, heat capacity, thermal conductivity) and after a duration of 6s a value of 0.85mm is found, that is therefore the spatial resolution of the fields evaluated.

7. LOCAL AND GLOBAL ANALYSIS

7.1 Definitions

The transition from the thermal measurements to the cyclic dissipated energy can be performed in several ways. The first one is to consider a given area and to base the analysis on the evolution along time of the mean temperature. This is called in the following “**global analysis**”: the cyclic dissipated energy is computed from the temperature evolution averaged on the gage length area. This evaluation is especially relevant for a comparison to the mechanical data, evaluated also in a mean manner with the extensometer (for the case of dogbone samples) [6].

The second one keeps the same idea of considering the average temperature but on a much smaller area. Actually, during the last loading step (test led until failure), a hot spot (small zone in the sample with a higher temperature than the neighborhood, see **fig. 11**) is observed, this zone is identified as the initiation location, previous to the sample failure (i.e. creation of a crack). The calculation of the cyclic dissipated energy using the temperature evolution averaged on the area of the local hot spot has also been performed. This is called in the following “**local analysis**”. This second analysis is of interest to relate accurately the dissipated energy leading to failure for the precise location of initiation.

The last way is to consider the full field of temperature in order to obtain directly the map of cyclic dissipated energy (see **section. 6**). For each result presented in the following, the type of analysis will be specified.

Figure 11. Hot spot location.

7.2 Results

On figure 12 the cyclic dissipated energy over the failure zone (method of calculation explained in the sections 4 and 5) and the field of cyclic dissipated energy (method of calculation explained in the section 6) are shown. It is noticed that for the case of dogbone samples, the highest dissipation zone is the zone of the initiation of the crack; however for the case of Wavy 1 samples, the initiation is localized over the zone of thickness increase (divergent zone), that is not the highest dissipation zone.

Figure 12. Local analysis and field of cyclic dissipated energy of dogbone and Wavy1 samples

8. IDENTIFICATION OF A FATIGUE CRITERION FROM THE THERMAL MEASUREMENTS (LOCAL ANALYSIS)

On the graph plotting the cyclic dissipated energy (local analysis, see fig. 12) versus the nominal stress amplitude, 3 regimes seem to appear (see fig. 13).

Figure 13. Regimes of the dissipated energy- nominal stress amplitude curve.

An energetic fatigue criterion is suggested [6], relating the number of cycles leading to initiation N to the cyclic dissipated energy Δ^* (local analysis), throughout a power law relation:

$$\Delta^* = CN^{-b} \quad (9)$$

Where C and b are the parameters to identify.

Two sets (Δ^*, N) are needed to identify the parameters.

The first set (Δ_A^*, N_A) is obtained from the last block that ran until the sample failure (see fig. 14).

The second set (Δ_B^*, N_B) is obtained from the cyclic dissipated energy-stress amplitude curve following these steps:

- A fitting using the points of the second regime is performed (black lines on the fig. 14) and the intersection of this line with the stress amplitude axis is evaluated.
- It is assumed that this intersection gives the stress amplitude leading to 10^6 cycles (noted σ_{a-10^6}). The second set $(\Delta_B^*, 10^6)$ is therefore given by the Δ_B^* corresponding to σ_{a-10^6} (see fig. 14).

Figure 14. Identification of the fatigue criterion.

The identification of the fatigue criterion is performed and several classical fatigue tests are achieved to verify the accuracy of the criterion (see **fig. 15**). A good correlation between the predictions of the fatigue criterion and the fatigue lifetime measured by classical fatigue tests is verified for each family of samples. The fatigue criterion identified over Wavy 1 samples is close to the one identified over Dogbone samples.

Figure 15. Comparison between the fatigue criterion and classical fatigue tests (Dogbone and Wavy 1 samples).

9. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The suggested protocol to evaluate the field of cyclic dissipated energy allows for describing the thermomechanical gradients that show the stress concentration in the case of Dogbone samples (the fiber orientation is homogenous) and the heterogeneity of the microstructure in the case of Wavy 1 samples. The accurate spatial and thermal resolution allows for detecting the zone of the fatigue initiation (hot spot).

The protocol suggested to identify quickly the fatigue properties of SFRT has been applied and the parameters of a fatigue criterion, based on the cyclic dissipated energy, have been challenged and successfully correlated to classical fatigue tests. Using this approach it is possible to predict the full deterministic fatigue curve using only one sample and the duration of the whole test is less than one day (for each case of sample). It is also important to underline that the approach is based on the evaluation of the dissipated energy, and not directly on temperature, that is not an intrinsic parameter. The approach developed here is therefore avoiding the dependencies on frequency, sample geometry, thermal conditions. In the case developed in this paper the energetic fatigue criterion identified over Dogbone samples is close to the one identified over Wavy 1 samples, giving a first validation of the prediction of the fatigue behavior of a complex sample from a simple one, the next step is to challenge the predictions over more complex cases of structural samples and also for real structures.

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